

MELAMİN EMDİRİLMİŞ ATIK KAĞITLARIN KUŞELEME İŞLEMLERİNDE DEĞERLENDİRİLMESİ

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Özet

Bu çalışmada kuşe kağıt üretimi için uzun ve kısa lifli kağıt hamuru harmanları kullanılarak 80 ± 5 gramajlarında kağıtlar üretilmiştir. Kuşe pigmenti olarak öğütülmüş kalsiyum karbonat (GCC) ve öğütülmüş melaminli kağıtlar, bağlayıcı olarak nişasta ve viskozite ayarlayıcı olarak karboksimetil selüloz kullanılarak kuşe harçları hazırlanmıştır. Kuşe harcı size-preste üretilen kağıtlara 3,2 bar atm basıncı altında 3 m/sn hızla her iki yüzey uygulanmıştır. GCC ve öğütülmüş melaminli kağıtlar ile kuşelenen kağıtlar fiziksel, optik özellik ve yüzey düzgünlüğü testlerine tabi tutulmuştur. Elde edilen deney sonuçlarına göre, kuşe kağıt üretiminde kuşe pigmenti olarak kalsiyum karbonat içerikli dolgu minerallerine ek bir malzeme olarak atık melamin emdirilmiş kağıtların öğütülerek kuşe harcı içinde kullanılabilirliği tespit edilmiştir. Atık melamin emdirilmiş kağıtların kullanım yerinden dolayı kuşelenen kağıtların suya ve neme karşı olan direncini de olumlu yönde etkilemiştir. Yüzey düzgünlüğü, fiziksel ve optik özellik değerleri de diğer kuşe pigmentleri gibi olumlu yönde kağıt yüzeyine katkı sağlayarak kuşe harcında kullanılabilirliğini göstermiştir. Ancak GCC ile kuşelenen kağıtların fiziksel ve optik özellik değerlerini olumlu yönde etkilerken suya ve neme karşı olan direncin atık melaminli kağıtlardan elde edilen kuşe pigmenti kadar etkili olmadığı sonucuna varılmıştır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Atık melaminli kağıt, öğütülmüş kalsiyum karbonat, kağıt, kuşeleme

Abstract

In this study, papers with a basis weight of 80 ± 5 gsm were produced for coated paper production using blends of long and short fiber paper pulps. Coating colors were prepared using ground calcium carbonate (GCC) and ground waste melamine-impregnated papers (MEK) as coating pigments, starch as a binder, and carboxymethyl cellulose as a viscosity modifier. The coating color was applied to both surfaces of the size-pressed papers at a speed of 3 m/s under a pressure of 3.2 bar. Papers coated with GCC and MEK were subjected to physical, optical, and surface roughness tests. According to the experimental results obtained, the feasibility of using waste melamine-impregnated papers as an additional material to calcium carbonate-based filler minerals in coating colors for coated paper production was determined. The use of waste melamine-impregnated papers positively affected the resistance of coated papers to water and moisture due to their origin of use. Surface roughness, physical, and optical values demonstrated the applicability of waste melamine-impregnated papers in coating colors, contributing positively to the paper surface, similar to other coating pigments. However, it was concluded that while papers coated with GCC positively influenced physical and optical properties, their resistance to water and moisture was not as effective as the coated papers obtained from waste melamine-impregnated papers.

Keywords: Waste melamine-impregnated papers, ground calcium carbonate, paper, coating

INTRODUCTION

Writing-printing papers are papers characterized by high optical properties, making them suitable for both writing and printing. These papers are manufactured from either chemical cellulose or a combination of chemical cellulose and mechanical wood pulp with a specific composition structure. Depending on their intended use, these papers undergo a coating process (Çiçekler, 2019).

To enhance the printing characteristics of paper and cardboard, two common methods are widely employed. The first involves passing the paper through a super calender after adding a filler material to the fiber suspension during the papermaking stage, typically in the range of 18-25% (Tutuş ve ark., 2018). This process helps regulate the surface of the paper by organizing small-sized filler particles, thus improving its printing properties. The second method aims to provide a regular and homogeneous surface to the paper after its production. This process, similar to what plasterers do to walls, involves smoothing out surface irregularities through an application of a coating consisting of mineral substances and adhesives. This process is known as paper coating or art paper production. Ground calcium carbonate (GCC), precipitated calcium carbonate (PCC), kaolin, and calcite, which are pigments containing high-purity calcium carbonate, commonly find application in the paper industry due to their high optical properties. These pigments are incorporated into coating solutions, forming a high-quality type of paper with improved writing and printing capabilities (Sönmez, 2008). Coated papers, with their high whiteness and brightness, enhance print quality and product appeal. Calcium carbonate pigments, naturally high in purity, are preferred in the paper industry as fillers and constituents of coating solutions (Eroğlu and Usta, 2004).

In response to the increasing demand for natural and economical products globally and in Turkey, the production of melamine-coated panels is rising proportionally with the resin-impregnated paper production. This increase in production also leads to a rise in the quantity of waste melamine-impregnated papers. The recycling of waste papers generated in the paper impregnation and surface coating sector is crucial within the scope of zero waste. Therefore, waste melamine-impregnated papers are collected and evaluated in various studies (Öz, 2019). The aim of this study is to determine the effects of both ground calcium carbonate (GCC), commonly used as both a filler pigment and a coating material in coated paper production, and ground and sieved waste melamine-impregnated papers (MEK), added as an additional component, on the optical and physical properties of coated papers obtained through the coating process. The study focuses on evaluating how GCC and MEK impact the characteristics of coated papers produced through the coating process.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this study, coating color was prepared following the existing coating recipes in the market, utilizing waste melamine-impregnated papers (MEK), ground calcium carbonate (GCC), carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC), and starch. The paper production involved the use of pre-bleached short and long fibers obtained from the market. Waste melamine-impregnated papers were sourced from manufacturing companies, fragmented to micron-sized particles using a stone mill, and sieved through a shaker screen to obtain sub-200 mesh powder samples. The GCC, CMC, and starch used in the study were commercially purchased. This project was conducted at Kahramanmaraş Sütçü İmam University, Faculty of Forestry, and the paper and cardboard production laboratory.

Paper Production and Coating Process

Blends of bleached short fibers (70%) and long fibers (30%), commonly used in the paper industry, were gradually beaten in a laboratory-scale Hollander beater up to 35 ± 5 °SR. Paper production was then carried out on a semi-automatic Rapid Kothen RK-21 paper machine using the beaten pulps with a grammage of 80 ± 5 gsm. For the coating color, suspensions of 50% concentration of waste melamine-impregnated papers (MEK) and ground calcium carbonate (GCC), and 15% concentration of starch were separately prepared. The prepared mixtures were stirred until homogenized in a beaker based on the proportions given in Table 1. Two different coating experiments were conducted using 100% MEK and 100% GCC in the coating color.

Table 1. Coating Color Preparation Recipe

No	MEK (%)	GCC (%)	Starch (%)	CMC (%)
1	0	0	0	0
2	100	100	15	0.3
3	0	100	15	0.3

The prepared coating color was poured between two cylinders in the size-press apparatus, applying it to both surfaces of the paper at a speed of 3 m/s under a pressure of 3.2 bars. The resulting coated papers were conditioned in a chamber with a temperature of 23 ± 1 °C and relative humidity of $65 \pm 1\%$ for 24 hours before undergoing optical and physical property tests.

Determination of Physical and Optical Properties

The coated papers, conditioned in the chamber for 24 hours, were subjected to physical and optical tests in accordance with the standards provided in Table 2 below.

Table 2. Physical and Optical Tests Applied to Coated Papers and Their Standards

Physical and Optical Tests	Standards
Grammage (gr/m^2)	TAPPI T 410 om-88
Thickness (μ)	TAPPI T 411 om-89
Bulkiness (cm^3/gr) and Density (gr/cm^3)	TAPPI T 411 om-89
Breaking length (m)	TAPPI T 494 om-01
Burst index ($\text{kPa m}^2/\text{gr}$)	TAPPI T 403 om-91
Tear index ($\text{mN.m}^2.\text{gr}$)	TAPPI T 414 om-88
COBB (gr/m^2)	ISO 535
Brightness (%ISO)	ISO/DIS 2470
Whiteness (%ISO)	ISO 11475
Opacity (%ISO)	ISO/DIS 2471
Yellowness (E313)	ASTM E313
Surface Roughness	ISO 4287

For the determination of physical and optical properties, 3 repetitions were performed for each experiment, and the averages were calculated.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Physical Properties of Coated Papers

Table 3 provides findings regarding some physical properties of papers coated with GCC and MEK. The coating process has led to significant changes in the tensile strength, burst indices, and tear indices of the papers.

Table 3. Findings on Some Physical Properties of Papers Coated with GCC and MEK.

	Breaking length (m)	Burst index (kPam ² /gr)	Tear index (mN.m ² /gr)	Density (gr/cm ³)	Bulkiness (cm ³ /gr)	COBB (gr/cm ²)
Control (uncoated)	3378	1.42	7.86	0.62	1.61	175
Coated with GCC	3117	1.68	6.26	0.73	1.38	155
Coated with MEK	4791	2.53	6.64	0.61	1.66	134

Compared to the control sample, papers coated with GCC and MEK show a respective decrease of -7.72% and an increase of 41.83% in tensile strength values. The burst indices exhibit an increase of 18.31% and 78.17%, while tear indices decrease by 20.36% and 15.52%. Although no significant differences are observed in bulkiness and density values, notable improvements are identified in COBB values. The surface roughness values indicating the surface properties of coated papers are provided in Table 4 below.

Table 4. Findings on The Surface Roughness Properties of Papers Coated with GCC and MEK

	Ra (µm)	Rq (µm)	Rz (µm)
Control (uncoated)	3.623	4.516	21.779
Coated with GCC	2.202	2.755	13.732
Coated with MEK	3.081	3.839	18.805

The Ra values of uncoated sample and coated papers (GCC, MEK) were determined to be 3.623, 2.202, and 3.081, respectively. The Rq values were 4.516, 2.755, and 3.839, while the Rz values were 21.779, 13.732, and 18.805. It was observed that the coated papers with GCC showed the best result in terms of surface roughness values, but the papers coated with MEK exhibited an improvement in surface roughness compared to the control sample.

Tutuş et al. (2013) conducted a study where they recycled papers, classified into categories such as newspaper, packaging, and writing-printing papers. They added 20-25-30% of precipitated calcium carbonate (PCC) and ground calcium carbonate (GCC) as fillers to the papers they produced, examining the optical and physical

properties of the resulting papers. As a result of their study, it was observed that the controlled production of PCC, with a more regular particle size, shape, and size distribution compared to GCC, improved adhesion to the papers and significantly reduced their physical properties. In another study, the addition of PCC and GCC in specific proportions as fillers to the paper was investigated, and it was found that the use of PCC and GCC resulted in decreases in the physical properties of the papers (Tutuş et al., 2012).

Optical Properties of Coated Papers

Below, Table 5 presents some optical properties of papers coated with PCC and GCC.

Table 5. Findings on Some Optical Properties of Papers Coated with GCC and MEK.

	Whiteness	Brightness	Yellowness	Opacity
Control (uncoated)	79.72	77.02	4.59	96.22
Coated with GCC	83.80	82.31	3.08	98.20
Coated with MEK	81.17	78.12	4.34	96.77

The coating process has led to a significant increase in the brightness and gloss values of the papers. Additionally, positive reductions in yellowness values have been observed. The reason for these increases is that the coating process with GCC and MEK improves the print quality of the paper surface. Compared to the control sample, whiteness values increased by 5.12% and 1.82%, while brightness values increased by 6.87% and 1.43% with GCC and MEK, respectively. Due to their inherent structures, GCC and MEK have contributed to the enhancements in optical property values. However, MEK, with its fibrous structure, and GCC, being 98% pure calcium carbonate, did not endow coated papers with the same level of optical property values.

In a study conducted by Tutuş et al. (2012), examining the physical and optical properties of paper with different proportions of PCC and GCC as fillers, brightness values were determined to be 80.08, 80.57, 80.52, 80.94, 83.06, and 81.15, while burst values were found to be 84.26, 84.37, 85.12, 85.31, 85.96, and 86.06. As a result of their studies, they noted that, due to its structure, PCC is whiter and brighter compared to kaolin, GCC, and other fillers, making it more suitable for achieving optimal brightness and gloss values in paper. Müdüroğlu and Arsoy (2013) aimed to achieve the best printing properties on a base cardboard by using different coating colors consisting of certain proportions of PCC and GCC. As a result of their study, they

observed that the cardboard surface had a homogeneous structure, the quality of the coating color improved, and there was an increase in the optical values of the paper.

Conclusion

As a result of this study, it has been determined that the addition of GCC results in a more homogeneous structure of the paper surface, leading to improvements in optical properties such as whiteness, brightness, yellowness, and opacity. Whiteness value is a crucial parameter influencing print quality, and the use of GCC and MEK as pigments in the coating process significantly increases this value. While the whiteness value of GCC used in coating color for art paper has increased more than MEK, papers coated with GCC negatively affect physical properties, whereas papers coated with MEK show an increase in physical property values. The observed increase in physical properties of papers coated with MEK is attributed to the fibrous structure and melamine adhesive present in MEK. However, it is observed that experimental papers coated with GCC provide the best optical properties, attributed to the high optical characteristics of the GCC pigment and its 98% purity in calcium carbonate. Consequently, this study concludes that, although MEK does not match GCC in the coating process, it enhances the optical properties of experimental papers and contributes higher physical property values compared to GCC coating. MEK is identified as usable in the coating process depending on the intended application of the paper, given its ability to impart high physical property values.

References

- Erođlu, H. ve Usta, M., (2004). *Kađıt ve Karton Üretim Teknolojisi I. Cilt. Selüloz ve Kađıt Sanayii Vakfı*, Trabzon.
- Çiçekler, M., (2019). *Birincil ve İkincil Lif Karışımlarının Yazı Tabı, Oluklu Mukavva ve Gazete Kađıdı Üretiminde Kullanımının Araştırılması*. Doktora Tezi, Kahramanmaraş Sütçü İmam Üniversitesi, Kahramanmaraş.
- Müdürođlu, M., Arsoy, Z., (2013). “The advantages of using Adacal nano PCC (Precipitated Calcium Carbonate) in production of coated carton. The Abstracts of the 1st International Porous and Powder Materials Symposium and Exhibition PPM”. Pp. 63. İzmir/Turkey
- Öz, E., (2019). *Kâđıt Kaplama Atıklarının Yonga Levha Üretiminde Kullanılması ve Özelliklere Etkisi*. Yüksek Lisans Tezi, Bartın Üniversitesi, Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Bartın.
- Sönmez, S., (2008). *Kartonun Yüzey Özelliklerinin Deđiştirilerek Basılabilirlik Niteliđinin Geliştirilmesi*. Doktora Tezi, Marmara Üniversitesi, İstanbul/Türkiye
- Tutuş, A., Çiçekler, M., Kazaskerođlu, Y., Müdürođlu, M., (2012). “Effects of Precipitated Calcium Carbonate (PCC) on optical and physical properties of paper. 8th International Minerals Symposium”. pp.147-152. İstanbul/Turkey
- Tutuş, A., Çiçekler, M., Özdemir, A., Okan, O.T., (2013). “Effects of Precipitated Calcium Carbonate (PCC) on optical properties of waste paper. International Caucasian Forestry Symposium”. pp.884-887. Artvin/Turkey.